

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT AND MARKETING PERFORMANCE OF PORT HARCOURT BOUTIQUES

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Abstract

In the context of globalized markets, supply chain management (SCM) practices play a critical role in enhancing marketing performance for businesses. This study examines the influence of SCM practices on the marketing performance of boutiques in Port Harcourt. Adopting a quantitative causal research design, the study tested four hypotheses. The population comprised 889 registered boutiques, with a sample of 269 boutiques selected using the Krejcie and Morgan table. Data were collected from 538 respondents—including sales representatives and customer relationship managers—via a structured five-point Likert scale questionnaire. Validity was established through expert review and previous research, while reliability was confirmed using SPSS version 22.0. Analysis via simple regression revealed that strategic supplier partnerships have a very strong, significant, and positive influence on customer patronage and brand awareness. Additionally, information sharing also exhibited a strong, significant, and positive influence on customer patronage and brand awareness. The study concludes that effective SCM practices significantly enhance marketing performance in boutiques. It is recommended that boutique managers continually modernize strategic supplier partnerships and information-sharing mechanisms to sustain and improve marketing outcomes.

Keywords: *Supply Chain Management, Strategic Supplier Partnership, Information Sharing, Customer Patronage, Brand Awareness*

Introduction

The Boutique industry is fast growing as most young Nigerians find it easy to navigate, and become established entrepreneurs. Boutiques are major players amidst the small and medium enterprises (SMEs) which are often considered the engine of economic growth and equitable development in developing nations. They are labour intensive, capital saving and capable of creating job opportunities for many etc Lalkaka (1997) as cited in (Mba & Emeti 2014). A Boutique is a retail shop that offers clothes, fabric, accessories and other fashion related products to a specific target market for customer satisfaction and profit maximization (Sabrina 2022). Successful boutiques place high emphasis on product quality and adhere to high set of standards. As far as opportunities are concerned, in the growing Boutique industry,

firms have chances to increase their business performance through adequate implementation of supply chain management practices. The term supply chain management practices involve a set of activities undertaken by organizations to promote effective management of their supply chains (Koh, Demirbag, Bayraktar, Tatoglu & Zaim, 2007). Supply chain management is a cohesive approach that begins with planning and controlling of materials, logistics, services, and information stream etc from suppliers, manufacturers to the customers; it opens up an important trajectory in marketing management practices to achieve optimum marketing performance in contemporary organizations (Ibrahim & Hamid 2016). Concurrent to the focus on customer value, the marketplace in which businesses operate today is widely recognized as being complex and turbulent (Goldman, Nagel & Preiss 1995), and the application of supply chain management practices aims to improve profitability, brand awareness, customer response, engagement, deliver value to the customers and improve the interconnection and interdependence among firms which all translates to effective marketing performance. Marketing performance is the alliance between stated marketing goals and actual results (Sorina, Marius & Nicoleta, 2013). This is reflected in the assessment of supply chain management practices, which are the anchors of company's worth.

Unfortunately, Asil, (2005) identified some major glitches in contemporary small and medium enterprises (SMEs) like Boutiques in Port Harcourt they include: lack of adequate entrepreneurial skills, poor management practices, low return on investment, high rate of enterprise mortality, overbearing business environment, constrained market access, lack of skills in international trade, bureaucracy, no access to relevant information. According to the Lagos Business School Insight (2022), most small and medium enterprises (SMEs) die naturally within their first five years of existence, others go into extinction between the sixth and tenth year while only about five to ten percent (5 to10%) survive, thrive and grow due to inadequate marketing research, poor marketing strategies and programs among others (Mba & Emeti 2014).

A close search of previous studies failed to connect supply chain management practices to marketing performance (Koh et al. 2007; Nimeh, Abdallah & Sweis, 2018). The influence of effective supply chain management practices on marketing performance is a progressively significant area of concentration in the academic and the business world. Obviously, in today's post-modern era, marketing performance is a valuable force to improve business profit and sustainable growth. But so far, little information is documented or less obtainable on how supply chain management practices influence marketing performance of Boutiques in Port Harcourt. Additionally, considerable number of empirical studies on supply chain management practices in literature are mainly in relation with sustainability, competitive advantage and organizational performance (Govindan, Azevedo, Carvalho & Cruz-Machado, 2014; Li, Ragu-Nathan, RaguNathan & Rao, 2006), and supply chain performance effectiveness (Ibrahim & Hamid, 2014), none examined the influence of supply chain management practices on marketing performance in the Port Harcourt context. Hence, the crux of this study is to empirically examine how supply chain practices and strategy implementation can influence and improve marketing performance which translates to

profitability, long-term growth and survival (Poi & Ihunwo, 2021). Figure 1 below illustrates the conceptual framework.

Figure 1: A Conceptual Framework of the influence of Supply Chain Management Practices on Marketing Performance of Boutiques in Port Harcourt

Source: Researcher’s Conceptualization (2022) as adapted from: (Grønholdt, & Martensen, 2006; Ahmad & Saifudin, 2014).

Research Questions

Drawing on the above conceptual framework, the study provides answers to the following research questions:

- i) To what extent does strategic supplier partnership influence marketing performance of Boutiques in Port Harcourt?
- iii) To what extent does information sharing influence marketing performance of Boutiques in Port Harcourt?

Literature Review

Relevant literature on the study variables were reviewed, the literature review covers theoretical framework, major concepts of the study and previous empirical studies.

Theoretical Foundation

The study mirrors the theory of Transaction cost economics (TCE) articulated below due to its bearing on supply chain management practices and marketing performance.

Transaction Cost Economics (TCE)

A business transaction is a finalized arrangement between a customer and a supplier/vendor to exchange goods, services, or financial assets in return for money. It lies at the root of all marketing efforts and have long been considered fundamental to marketing thought and practice (Bagozzi, 1978). The importance of business transactions is evident in our day-to-day experiences, which are typically filled with a variety of

dealings in both our personal and professional lives, whether in cash, credit, internally or externally. They range from purchasing goods, sale of goods, paying interest, wages, loans, rent and other utilities to posting an online review. Therefore, management scientists have devoted substantial effort in trying to understand them. In 1937 Ronald H. Coase was the first to spot the relevance of understanding the costs of transacting. As a standard model, transaction cost economics (TCE) began solemnly in the late 1960s and early 1970s as an attempt to appreciate and make empirical estimates of “the make-or-buy decisions” occasionally called “the canonical (TCE) case” in business organizations (Ketokivi & Mahoney, 2020). The theory of Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) explains how business transactions are carried out in volatile business environments. The theory of Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) is essentially focused on transactions that involve delicate commitments, transactions that are intricate, frequent, risky and hard to reverse without substantial economic loss (Williamson, 1975, 1985).

During the early formulation of transaction cost economics (TCE), the ultimate aim of proponents was to understand the details of different transactions involving two or more exchange partners (Santos & Eisenhardt, 2005). Hence, it is among the most commonly referenced firms’ theories in marketing and supply chain management research because the make-or-buy decision gamely aligns with some of the fundamental issues on how firms manage their supply chains to achieve effective organizational performance (Ketokivi & Mahoney, 2020). For instance, Kotler (1972) iterates that marketing’s principal goals culminate with market transactions and customer satisfaction. Generally, marketing performance is a function of strategies that firms use to facilitate transactions and how consumers respond to them (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001; Kohli & Jaworski, 1990; Oliver, 1999). In the field of supply chain management, Williamson, (1971) explained that Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) is a substitute exposition of vertical integration where a firm acquires or establishes its suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, and retail locations instead of outsourcing them in order to minimize cost. Rindfleisch, (2019) identified the grave effects of opportunism in transactions, because of the inclination of most exchange partners to be dishonest, selfish and impede adequate supplier partnership and information sharing (John 1984; Hill, 1990; Williamson, 1985 Williamson, 2000).

Conceptual Review

Concept of Supply Chain Management Practices (SCMPs)

A supply chain is a network of facilities and distribution alternatives that procures and transforms raw materials into intermediate and finished goods, and distributes these finished goods to customers. Wisner, Tan & Leong (2012) defined supply chain management as the integration of exchange partners and key business processes from raw material extraction to the end user, including all intermediate processing like transportation and warehousing and final sale to the end user. To this end, supply chains management (SCM) boost customer service and satisfaction by meeting customers’ expectations, ensuring on time delivery, providing after sales support, enhance business performance and profit all stakeholders (Chopra & Meindl, 2001).

Supply chain management practices (SCMPs) are a set of operations that integrate suppliers, producers, distributors, and customers, in order to improve supply chain performance (Barros, 2006; Koh et al. 2007). The concept of supply chain management practices (SCMPs) comprises of agreed-upon objectives like; information sharing, process integration, long-term relationships management etc (Said, 2021).

Hence, supply chain management practices (SCMPs) are a set of patterns that combines every strata of the supply chain to enhance business performance (Barros, 2006; Koh et al. 2007) as cited in (Alahmad, 2021). Ibrahim & Hamid, (2014) indicate that supply chain management practices (SCMPs) are methods utilized in managing the combination and synchronization of supply, demand and relationship with supply chain partners in order to satisfy customers effectively and profitably. Many scholars have examined the fundamental dimensions of supply chain management practices (SCMPs); information and analysis, process management, strategic planning (Flynn & Flynn, 2005), strategic supplier partnership, customer relationship, information sharing, information quality, internal lean practices and postponement (Li et al. 2005) and information sharing, customer relationship, strategic supplier partnership, material flow management and corporate culture (Chin et al. 2011) as cited in (Ibrahim & Hamid, 2014). This study in line with Flynn & Flynn, (2005) adopts strategic suppliers' partnership and information sharing as the dimensions of supply chain management practices. Scholars have found that outsourcing, firms' partnerships with suppliers, relevant information sharing in the chains of supply, product quality, procurement activities, customer relationship management, both inward and outward supply chain integration and all other flows within the supply chain incorporates supply chain practices (Tan, Kannan & Handfield, 1998; Abdelsalam & Siddig, 2014; Djoko, Afghan, Ismail, Haizam, & Saudi, 2019; Poi & Okwandu, 2021).

Strategic Suppliers' Partnership

Strategic suppliers are possibly the most long-term distributors who provides goods and services that are critical to the success of the firm. For this reason, the relationship must be nurtured and maintained. Strategic suppliers' partnership is defined as the long-term, mutually beneficial relationship between a firm and its suppliers. Strategic partnership between organizations promotes shared benefits and enduring collaboration in key strategic areas like technology, products, and market (Yoshino & Rangan, 1995; Thatte, 2007). Closer relationships between the firm and suppliers could create significant value, strategic alignment, communication and trust, cross-functional engagement and help supply chains become more resilient (Gutierrez, Kothari, Mazuera & Schoenherr, 2020). Strategic suppliers' partnership is a long-term premeditated alliance of two or more firms in a supply chain to enable shared effort and teamwork in different fundamental value creating activities, for instance; research and product development, production, marketing etc with the purpose of cumulating profits to all stakeholders (Maheshwari et al. 2006; Li et al. 2006) as cited in (Agus, Makhbul & Hassan, 2008). Tsai, (2007) found that strategic supplier partnership is a mediator of organizational performance. Thus, strategic supplier partnership fully facilitates the relationship between a lean supply chain strategy and responsive supply chain (Binalla,

2019). Agus et al. (2008) submits that strategic supplier partnership practices are substantially associated with product quality performance and business performance.

Information Sharing

The worth of germane information is capitalized on only when dispersed adequately, information flow is a vital aspect of supply chain management; it is one of the major supply chain “flows” (Lambert, Cooper & Pagh 1998) as cited in (Poi & Okwandu, 2021). According to Savolainen, (2017), information sharing is an activity through which thoughts, views, truths and documents are moved from an individual (or group) to others. More recently, Poi & Okwandu, (2021) found that information sharing does not necessitate customer satisfaction but boosts customer loyalty, because for it to directly influence customer satisfaction, timely information must be shared and managed before sales, during sales and after sales. Information sharing involves activities of dispensing valuable information among individuals, and structures in an open environment. Due to the volatile nature of today’s business environment, Khaliunaa & Ramzani, (2019) indicate that information sharing between supply chain firms is done at operational, tactical, and strategic levels. In supply chain relationships, business-based data between supply chain partners are shared through software technologies such as electronic data interchange (EDI) or Enterprise resource planning (ERP), Vendor Managed Inventory (VMI), Collaborative Planning, Forecasting, and Replenishment (CPFR), Continuous Replenishment Program (CRP), and sharing of Point-of-Sale (POS) demand information. Omar, Ramayah, May-Chuin, Sang & Siron, (2010) opined that information sharing ought to consider issues like; “what exactly to share”, “whom to share”, “how to share”, and “when to share” in order to reduce cost of sharing, information deficit or surplus and enhance the overall supply chain performance. According to the United States of America Department of Homeland Security (DHS), information sharing is a vital resource for critical infrastructure security and resilience (Lee, 2022). Likewise, the Office for Victims of Crime, (n.d) indicated that organizations need to strike the required balance of protecting and sharing sensitive information because sharing too much information can become detrimental to both customers and organizations. The inability to create a benign and effective information-sharing system is counterproductive to parties involved.

Marketing Performance

In recent years, marketing experts have been under incessant pressure to validate their involvement and contribution to organizational performance. It has been maintained extensively that an inability to justify for the contribution of marketing strategies and programs has dented its reputation within organizations (Sullivan & Abela, 2007). To ensure that marketing efforts are justified, marketing practitioners are investing in developing performance measurement parameters (Sullivan & Abela, 2007). Marketing performance is the metrics and results that the marketing function utilizes to regulate how marketing inputs produce outputs in line with marketing objectives for organizations (Wrike, 2022). Maclayton & Nwokah, (2012) opined that marketing performance is an expression used by marketing researchers and practitioners to assess the efficiency and effectiveness of marketing strategies and programs. Allocadia

(2020) as cited in Poi & Okwandu, (2021) stated that marketing performance is basically marketing yields in comparison with marketing input. Marketing performance is the alignment between the marketing team's stated goals and objects versus actual results. Measuring performance of a firm's marketing efforts effectively can in due course enhance the marketing strategy evaluation process and return on investment (Caveney, 2021). According to Wrike, (2022), marketing performance is measured with different metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs), including return on investment, cost per sale, cost per lead, conversion rate, and customer lifetime value, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty. This study focused on customer patronage and brand awareness as non-financial subjective measures of marketing performance in consonance with (Grønholdt & Martensen, 2006).

Customer Patronage

The customer is as old as business, in fact some prospective customers are older than the business. Before developing products and services, marketing-oriented organizations conduct market research to determine and understand their target customers expectations and preferences. A customer is an individual or organization who buys products (goods or services) from a business. According to eProject Library, (2022), a customer is any person or organization who might have interest in buying, or has bought, products or services from a firm. Generally, they include, current customers, past customers and potential customers. Drucker, (1973) indicates that the main aim of every business is to "create customers" which is the essence of the marketing concept. Business success is anchored on customer patronage, it plays a vital role in a firm's ability to reach and appeal to potential customers as well as retain existing customers. Customer patronage is the degree to which customers sustain purchases for a particular product and brand over a period of time (Nyakweba, Wesonga & Bosire, 2015). Customer Patronage is a marketing performance metric that shows customers' positive or negative perspective based on their predispositions and experiences with a product, service and brand. (Cambell, 2019) as cited in (Okeke, 2020). Customer patronage simply mirrors the degree of customers' devotion to a product or brand. More often than not, customer service and satisfaction precede consistent patronage because customers choose to patronize firms based on their perception of the brand Deviney (1998) as cited in (Chikere & Poi, 2021a). When customers are satisfied and sustained, they become profitable assets and the rate of their patronage reflects the overall health of the business (Poi & Nwokah, 2022).

Brand awareness

A brand is a designation, an emblem or a blend of both used to identify and differentiate an organization from its competitors. It includes the firm's logo, spokesperson, voice, message, or an experience that allows the business to function and thrive in the market place Maclayton, & Nwokah, (2002) as cited in (Chikere & Poi, 2021a). Brand awareness is a major marketing performance indicator that occurs when customers are familiar with a brand. This is connected to the customer's ability to remember previous connections with the brand (Kotler & Pfertch, 2007). In agreement, Walgrove (2020) opine that brand awareness is the way in which consumers recognize and remember the brand. Brand awareness embodies how conversant

the target market is with the image of the brand and how well they identify it. Decker, (2022) indicate that brands with high brand awareness are usually referred to as “trendy”, “buzzworthy” or simply “popular”. The image of the brand emerges through the psychological fulfilment of customers which is tied to how aware they are of it. Brand image is created by the effective implementation and monitoring of marketing strategies and programs that endears a strong and unique associations to the brand. In consumers’ awareness these associations are measured based on customer experiences, information received on the brand, the brand association to the specific company, products, people, events, country etc (Seturi, 2017). Keller, (1993), identified brand recall and brand recognition as major components of brand awareness as it is the degree to which customers and prospects are able to remember and identify a brand under diverse conditions.

Empirical Review on Supply Chain Management Practices and Marketing Performance

Koh, et al. (2007) examined the impact of supply chain management practices on performance of SMEs. The study adopted a variance-based structural equation modeling approach; partial least squares method was used to test its hypotheses. Data for the study were collected from a sample of two hundred and three (203) manufacturing (SMEs) operating in fabricated metal products and general-purpose machinery within the city of Istanbul in Turkey. The results indicate that both factors of strategic collaboration and lean practices (SCLP) and outsourcing and multisuppliers (OMS), do not have a significant and direct impact on supply chain management-related organizational performance. Also, as the direct relationship between the two performance-constructs was found significant, it indicates that (SCM) practices might directly influence operational performance of (SMEs).

Nsikan, Okon, Sylvester & Uduak, (2019) examined supply chain management practices and hospital operational efficiency: The Nigerian example. The study adopted a survey design on a population of five hundred and eighty-four (584) healthcare supply chain executives. A structured questionnaire was used to obtain primary data which were analyzed quantitatively. The study found that operational efficiency is significantly and positively influenced strategic supplier partnership, supplier selection decision, and integration of information communication technologies among supply chain partners. It concluded that exchange of timely inventory and demand data along the supply chain network can enhance supply operations efficiently.

Olapoju, (2019) studied supply chain management practices in Nigeria: Developing a framework for enhancement of supply chain management (SCM) for organizational performance. The main purpose of this study was to examine supply chain-management factors that could enhance the organizational performance in manufacturing firms. A quantitative approach was used and data were gathered from a population of four hundred (400) employees in manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Structural equation modelling with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) Version (21) was used to analyze the interrelationship among variables. The study found a positive and significant relationship between supply chain management practices and organizational performance

Sukati, Sanyal & Awaain, (2020) investigated supply chain management practices and organizational performance: An investigation from service industry. The purpose of the study was to assess how (SCM) is related to the performance of business organizations in the tourism service industry. A questionnaire was used for data collection which was administered to a total sample of eighty-five (85) managers in hospitality organizations (hotel, restaurant and transportation companies). The study found that strategic supplier partnership and organizational performance was positively and significantly related, customer relationship management can significantly impact on organizational performance, information sharing is significantly related to organizational performance, information technology can significantly impact on organizational performance and finally there was a significant relationship between internal operations and organizational performance.

Alahmad, (2021) studied the relationship between supply chain management practices and supply chain performance in Saudi Arabian firms. An empirical study was conducted on a sample of one hundred and ninety-six (196) firms, data were collected from the supply chain managers and those in top management in different industries in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. In addition to sequences of interviews conducted with managers of the supply chains, a theoretical model was developed depicting the relationship between supply chain management practices (SCMPs) and supply chain performance (SC performance). This model was also tested using multiple regression analysis. The research concluded that supply chain management practices (SCMPs), including supply chain planning (SC planning), level of information sharing (IS), customer relationship management (CRM), and supplier relationship management (SRM) are all positively related to supply chain performance.

Said, (2021) investigated supply chain practices and marketing performance of SMEs: a field study on furniture manufacturing in Egypt. The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of supply chain practices on the marketing performance of small and medium-sized furniture manufacturing enterprises in Egypt. The study applied to sixty-seven (67) enterprises in Damietta, Egypt. The study population was represented by two top directors of furniture companies either. Two 39-item- questionnaire of a five-point Likert-type scale was used for each enterprise with a total of 134 questionnaires. Internal consistency of one hundred and twenty (120) valid questionnaires by using Pearson correlation discovered that the questionnaire was stable and valid. The relationship between supply chain practices and marketing performance was analyzed with the Pearson moment correlation, the results show that a positive and significant relationship exist between supply chain practices indicators; (supplier relationship management, and customer relationship management) and marketing performance.

Poi & Okwandu, (2021) examined the relationship between supply chain integration and marketing performance of oil servicing firms in Nigeria. The study adopted an explanatory research design and primary data were obtained from ten (10) prominent oil servicing firms in Nigeria. The Spearman rank order correlation coefficient was used for data analysis and concluded that supply chain integration can

positively and significantly enhance marketing performance. Building on these findings the study proposed the following hypotheses:

Ho1: Strategic supplier partnership has no significant influence on customer patronage of boutiques in Port Harcourt.

Ho2: Strategic supplier partnership has no significant influence on brand awareness of boutiques in Port Harcourt.

Ho3: Information sharing has no significant influence on customer patronage of boutiques in Port Harcourt.

Ho4: Information sharing has no significant influence on brand awareness of boutiques in Port Harcourt.

Research Methodology

This study examined the influence of supply chain management practices on marketing performance of Boutiques in Port Harcourt. A quantitative and causal research approach was adopted; it focused on identifying the extent and nature of the “cause and effect” relationship between variables without any manipulation. The population of this study consists of eight hundred and eighty-nine (889) registered Boutiques in Port Harcourt, whose authentic list was derived from the Business Directory of the Rivers State Ministry of Commerce and Industry, and sample size of two hundred and sixty-nine (269) was attained with the Krejcie and Morgan table.

A self-structured questionnaire designed in the five-point Likert scale was used to obtained primary data from five hundred and thirty-eight (538) respondents (key informants; sales representatives and customer relationship managers), purposely chosen from the selected two hundred and sixty-nine (269) Boutiques, through a cross-sectional survey. The face validity of the questionnaire was established by professionals consisting of scholars and business practitioners with adequate knowledge of the subject matter. The construct and content validity were confirmed from previous researchers who used it, with slight adjustments. The research hypotheses were tested with the simple regression technique with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0. Table 1 shows the distribution and the collection pattern of the respondent’s questionnaire.

Table 1: Distribution and Retrieval of Questionnaire

S/n	Characteristics of questionnaire	Available Quantity	Percentage%
1.	Total number of copies produced and distributed	538	100
2.	Copies returned (receive of boutique used)	445	83
3.	Copies not returned (not received)	93	17
4.	Copies returned (received)	445	100
5.	Usable copies	334	75
6.	Unusable (Discarded)	111	25
	Usable rate	$\frac{334}{445} \times \frac{100}{1}$	75

Source: Field work (2022).

Table 1 illustrates the analysis of the distribution and collection pattern of respondents' questionnaire. Out of the five hundred and thirty-eight (538) copies of questionnaire that were distributed to the respondents, four hundred and forty-five (445) copies were returned, yielding a response rate of eighty-three percent (83%). The remaining ninety-three percent (93%) copies were not returned and accounted for. However, the return rate of eighty-three percent (83%) is well thought-out as high and excellent making an allowance for a minimum return rate of seventy percent (70%) as suggested by (Kothari 2011).

Hypotheses Testing

Ho₁: Strategic supplier partnership has no significant influence on customer patronage of boutiques in Port Harcourt.

Table 2: Influence of Strategic Supplier Partnership on Customer Patronage (N=334).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	
1	.983	.963	.961	2.6751	a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic Supplier Partnership

b. Criterion: Customer Patronage

Source: SPSS Window Output, Version 22.0 (Based on 2022 Field Survey Data).

Given that for hypothesis one, the significant is .000 which is less than 0.05; there is a significant, influence of strategic supplier partnering on customer patronage with the R (Coefficient of Correlation), there is 98.3% direct relationship between strategic suppliers partnership on customer patronage. R-square value of 96.3% shows that strategic supplier partnership can influence customer patronage to a very high degree. The results were presented in table 3.

Table 3: One-way ANOVA for the Difference in Mean between Strategic Supplier Partnership on Customer Patronage (N=334).

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.63	1	0.63	233.264	.0000
Within Groups	002	333	000		
Total	0.66200	334			

a. Criterion: Customer Patronage

b. Predictor: Strategic Supplier Partnership

Source: SPSS Window Output, Version 22.0 (Based on 2022 Field Survey Data).

Table 3 illustrates that there is difference in mean between strategic supplier partnership and customer patronage $F(df_B, df_W) = F(333, 1) = 233.264, p < 0.05$. Significant value is 0.00, $r(1, 333)$. This agrees with the regression result in Table 2.

Ho₂: Strategic supplier partnership has no significant influence on brand awareness of boutiques in Port Harcourt.

Table 4: Influence of Strategic Supplier Partnership on Brand Awareness (N=334).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate
1	.772	.764	.762	45343

a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic Supplier Partnership

b. Criterion Variable: Brand Awareness

Source: SPSS Window Output, Version 22.0 (Based on 2022 Field Survey Data).

Given that for hypothesis two, the significant is .000 which is less than 0.05; there is a significant, influence of strategic supplier partnership on brand awareness with the R (Coefficient of Correlation), there is 77.2% direct relationship between strategic supplier partnership and brand awareness. R-square value of 76.4 % shows that strategic supplier partnership can influence brand awareness to a high degree. The researcher also used ANOVA to test the hypothesis in this section. The results were presented in Table 5

Table 5: One-way ANOVA for the Difference in Mean between Strategic Supplier Partnering on Brand Awareness (N=334).

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	77.074	1	77.074	374.879	.0000
Within Groups	23.849	333	206		
Total	100.94	334			

a. Criterion variable: Brand Awareness

b. Predictor: Strategic Supplier Partnership

Source: SPSS Window Output, Version 22.0 (based on 2022 field survey data).

Table 5 shows that there is difference in mean between strategic supplier partnership and brand awareness $F(dfB,dfw) = F(333,1) = 374.879, p < 0.05$. Significant value is 0.00, $r(1,333)$. This agrees with the regression result in Table 4.

H03: Information sharing has no significant influence on customer patronage of boutiques in Port Harcourt.

Table 6: Influence of Information Sharing on Customer Patronage (N=334).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate
1	.727	.684	.682	.647

a. Predictors: Information Sharing

b. Criterion: Customer Patronage

Source: SPSS Window Output, Version 22.0 (Based on 2022 Field Survey Data).

Given that for hypothesis three, the significant is .000 which is less than 0.05; there is a significant, influence of information sharing on customer patronage with the R (Coefficient of Correlation), there is 72.7% direct relationship between information sharing and customer patronage. R-square value of 68.4% shows that information sharing can influence customer patronage to a high degree. The researcher also used ANOVA to test the hypothesis in this section. The results were presented in table 7.

Table 7: One-way ANOVA for the Difference in Mean between Information Sharing and Customer Patronage (N=334).

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3201393	1	3201393	648433	.0000
Within Groups	1481137	333		199595	
Total	4682530	334			

a. Criterion: Customer Patronage

b. Predictor: Information Sharing

Source: SPSS Window Output, Version 22.0 (Based on 2022 Field Survey Data).

Table 7 shows that there is difference in mean between information sharing and customer patronage $F(dfB,dfw) = F(333,1) = 648433, p < 0.05$. Significant value is 0.00, $r(1,333)$. This agrees with the regression result in Table 6.

Ho₄: Information sharing has no significant influence on brand awareness of boutiques in Port Harcourt.

Table 8: Influence of Information Sharing on Brand Awareness (N=334).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate
1	.764	.647	.645	.628

a. Predictors: (Constant), Information Sharing

b. Criterion: Brand Awareness

Source: SPSS Window Output, Version 22.0 (Based on 2022 Field Survey Data).

Given that for hypothesis four (Ho₄), the significant is .000 which is less than 0.05; there is a significant, influence of information sharing on brand awareness with the R (Coefficient of Correlation), there is 76.4% direct relationship between information sharing on brand awareness. R-square value of 64.7% shows that information sharing can influence brand awareness to a high degree. The researcher also used ANOVA to test the hypothesis in this section. The results were presented in Table 9.

Table 9: One-way ANOVA for the Difference in Mean between Information Sharing on Brand Awareness (N=334).

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	36496263	1	36496263	8.84184	.0000
Within Groups	118627	333	648		
Total	614870	334			

a. Criterion: Brand Awareness

b. Predictor: Information Sharing

Source: SPSS Window Output, Version 22.0 (based on 2022 field survey data).

Table 9 shows that there is difference in mean between information sharing and brand awareness $F(dfB, dfw) = F(333,1) = 8.84184, p < 0.05$. Significant value is 0.01, $r(1,333)$. This agrees with the regression result in Table 8.

Discussion of Findings

The study examined the influence of supply chain management practices on marketing performance of boutiques in Port Harcourt. The findings of empirical analysis revealed that all the elements of supply chain management practices (strategic suppliers' partnership and information sharing) can influence marketing performance (customer patronage and brand awareness) positively and significantly in boutiques in Port Harcourt. These findings support the reports of Nsikan et al. (2019) who examined supply chain management practices and hospital operational efficiency: The Nigerian example and found that strategic supplier partnership, supplier selection decision, and integration of information communication technologies can influence operational efficiency significantly and positively among supply chain partners. Our findings are also in agreement with the report of Sukati, et al. (2020) who studied supply chain management practices and organizational performance: An investigation from service industry. The study found that strategic supply chain partnership is positively and significantly related to organizational performance. The study iterated that information sharing is significantly related to organizational performance and information technology can significantly impact on organizational performance.

Similarly, the finding of Olapoju, (2019) on the relationship between supply chain management practices and organizational performance in Nigeria and found a positive and significant relationship between supply chain management practices and organizational performance. The finding is also in consonance with Said, (2021) who explored supply chain practices and marketing performance of SMEs: a field study on furniture manufacturing in Egypt and showed that a positive relationship exists between supply chain practices dimensions; (supplier relationship management and customer relationship management) and marketing performance. Similarly, our finding agrees with the theory of Transaction cost economics (TCE), that the element of opportunism in most transactions is an enemy to both supplier relationship management and information sharing (Rindfleisch, 2019). Finally, the finding is in sync with Poi & Okwandu, (2021) who analyzed the relationship between supply chain integration and marketing

performance of oil servicing firms in Nigeria and found that supply chain integration (strategic alliance and information sharing) can positively and significantly enhance marketing performance (customer satisfaction and customer loyalty) of oil servicing firms in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper concludes by showing that marketing performance is influenced supply chain management practices as shown in Boutiques in Port Harcourt. This study adds more to the body of knowledge on supply chain management practices and marketing performance. Drawing from the transaction cost economics (TCE); this study shows that marketing performance is a function of strategies that firms use to facilitate transactions and opportunism in transactions should be avoided due to its grave effects on supply chain partners. The paper recommends that supply chain management practices (strategic supplier partnership and information sharing) activities of boutiques should be tailored towards the attainments marketing performance.

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